

The Unjournal

Evaluation Summary and Metrics: "Maternal cash transfers for gender equity and child development: Experimental evidence from India"

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ABSTRACT¹

We organized two evaluations of the paper: "Maternal cash transfers for gender equity and child development: Experimental evidence from India" [1]. This trial involved moderate payments (about 10% of average household consumption) directly to new mothers' and pregnant women's bank accounts, along with light-touch messaging about nutrition. The Unjournal prioritized this in part because of the importance of understanding when *unconditional* transfers can help improve nutrition, as monitoring *conditional* transfers is expensive. The results were mixed, with increases in caloric intake and gains in children's functional development, but tightly bounded near-zero impacts on children's heights and weights. Both evaluators — experts in global health and child development — found a lot to like: "this is a timely study that adds insight"; "strengths include scale, comprehensiveness, and rigorous analysis of treatment effects and effect heterogeneity". They also offered substantial critiques and suggestions. Evaluator 1 had concerns about the use and reporting of the *Ages and Stages Questionnaire*. They also wanted more policy-relevant interpretation of the magnitudes, including "tangible and clinically meaningful conclusions", a concern shared by the evaluation manager. The second evaluator (Tsai) was puzzled by the "substantial gains in child development even in the absence of impacts on anthropometrics or any parenting/other behavioral 'plus' components", which contrasted with related work. They asked for a better explanation of the context, particularly concurrent *conditional* cash transfers (CCTs) and health services targeting early childhood. They were skeptical of the 'nutrition only helped for the high-sanitation subgroup' claim, noting that "other studies in LMICs have compared joint nutrition and sanitation interventions to only nutrition interventions directly, and effects on stunting, wasting, and underweight are not consistently better." They also asked about the "exclusion of breastmilk from child food consumption" accounting. To read these evaluations, please see the links below.

Evaluations

1. [Evaluator 1](#)
2. [Eleanor Tsai](#)

Overall ratings

We asked evaluators to provide overall assessments as well as ratings for a range of specific criteria.

I. Overall assessment (See footnote²)

II. Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5): On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' should this be published in?³ Note: 0= lowest/none, 5= highest/best.

	Overall assessment (0-100)	Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5)
Evaluator 1	70	3.1
Eleanor Tsai	85	4.2

See "[Metrics](#)" below for a more detailed breakdown of the evaluators' ratings across several categories. To see these ratings in the context of all Unjournal ratings, with some analysis, see our [data presentation here](#).⁴

See [here](#) for the current full evaluator guidelines, including further explanation of the requested ratings.

Evaluation summaries

Anonymous evaluator 1

This is a timely study that adds insight into whether and how unconditional cash transfers to mothers can improve their health and the health and development of their children in a low resource setting in India. Major comments include the need to think through equitable authorship, further describe certain aspects of the intervention (i.e., messaging provided to participants), and add detail to the methods around the use of the Ages and Stages Questionnaire.

Eleanor Tsai

Weaver et al. evaluate the first randomized trial of UCTs in India, examining impacts on a battery of measures of household spending, consumption, nutrition, and child growth and development. Strengths include scale, comprehensiveness, and rigorous analysis of treatment effects and effect heterogeneity. Critiques center around the interpretation of results in light of (1) findings from previous studies of cash transfers and integrated sanitation and nutrition interventions, and (2) the context of concurrent CCTs and health services targeting early childhood.

Metrics

Ratings

[See here](#) for details on the categories below, and the guidance given to evaluators.

	Evaluator 1			Evaluator 2	
	Anonymous			Eleanor Tsai	

Rating category	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*	Comments	Rating (0-100)	90% CI (0-100)*
Overall assessment ⁵	70	(65, 75)		85	(80, 90)
Claims, strength, characterization of evidence ⁶	85	(80, 90)		90	(80, 100)
Advancing knowledge and practice ⁷	90	(89, 91)		95	(90, 100)
Methods: Justification, reasonableness, validity, robustness ⁸	60	(58, 72)		85	(80, 90)
Logic & communication ⁹	85	(85, 85)		80	(75, 85)
Open, collaborative, replicable ¹⁰	30	(20, 40)	11	90	(80, 100)
Real-world relevance ^{12, 13}	88	(84, 92)		95	(90, 100)
Relevance to global priorities ^{14, 15}	88	(84, 92)		95	(90, 100)

Journal ranking tiers

[See here](#) for more details on these tiers.

	Evaluator 1		Evaluator 2	
	Anonymous		Eleanor Tsai	

Judgment	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI	Ranking tier (0-5)	90% CI
On a 'scale of journals', what 'quality of journal' <i>should</i> this be published in?	3.1	(2.9, 3.3)	4.2	(3.6, 5.0)
What 'quality journal' do you expect this work <i>will</i> be published in?	2.9	(2.1, 3.1)	4.1	(3.6, 4.6)
See here for more details on these tiers.	<p><i>We summarize these as:</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0.0: Marginally respectable/Little to no value • 1.0: OK/Somewhat valuable • 2.0: Marginal B-journal/Decent field journal • 3.0: Top B-journal/Strong field journal • 4.0: Marginal A-Journal/Top field journal • 5.0: A-journal/Top journal 			

Claim identification and assessment (summary)

For the full discussions, see the corresponding sections in each linked evaluation.

	Main research claim ¹⁶	Belief in claim ¹⁷	Suggested robustness checks ¹⁸	Important 'implication', policy, credibility ¹⁹

Evaluator 1 Anonymous	The authors claim that unconditional cash transfers to mothers in India increase calorie intake, dietary diversity, and nutrient consumption for mothers and children, that they narrow gender disparities in food consumption, and improve early childhood development.	Yes, I believe these claims are true as the data show.	I would like to see the estimates translated into more tangible and clinically meaningful conclusions.	As stated in my evaluation, I would like authors to be more clear in the meaning of their estimates, so that I could state something to the effect of: unconditional cash transfers to mothers in India, if scaled up, could results in an increase in X IQ points among young children living in resource limited settings.
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References

[1] Weaver, J., Sukhtankar, S., Niehaus, P., & Muralidharan, K. (2024). *Maternal Cash Transfers for Gender Equity and Child Development: Experimental Evidence from India* (Working Paper No. 32093). National Bureau of Economic Research. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w32093>

Evaluation manager's discussion

This was written by Sarah A. Reynolds. It is written directly addressing the authors, but the discussion should be of interest to other researchers and practitioners.

This study was chosen for evaluation because we recognize the tremendous impact it can have on helping policy makers consider contexts when implementing cash transfers and confirms that unconditional cash transfers are also used for improving nutrition; conditionalities – expensive to monitor – are not always required.

However, all of [the] authors are economists, and this paper has a much broader scope for impact beyond a single field. Thus, I have solicited evaluations from two experts in global health and child development. I find that they highlight some important ways in which you can strengthen your paper and reach a broader audience.

Evaluator 1 starts with a call for including investigators from the Global South. Though many of you seem to be from the Global South or at least those cultures, currently you are based in the US and have a position of privilege. Your work on the Global South shows your commitment to your roots, for which I commend you, and your success in your careers indicates that you are contributing to diversity locally. Thank you! The suggestion to add additional investigators is not one that need be done for this paper (since The Unjournal

is not a publication we do not have publication standards) but this is a growing trend in international Public Health journals of which you should be aware should you consider submitting for an audience broader than the economics audience. Perhaps you will bring this conversation into the field of economics as well!

Evaluator 2 challenges you to compare your work in more depth to other studies and speculate about why your findings are different from others. I understand that drawing conclusions from a small sample (# of studies) is uncomfortable for economists. However, this will be very useful to the readers to have your findings contextualized (which I acknowledge you have done to an extent already). This also leads nicely into the comment from both evaluators that a section on limitations is missing. This is also typical of public health publications and a great place to discuss the limited scope of the work, possible biases, implementation challenges, data challenges, and suggest further research that can build on your study. This is the perfect place to state that you have some thoughts about why your findings were different and more study is needed. A summary of the limitations in the discussion helps others know you have fully thought them through and were unable to address them for practical reasons.

Both evaluators also inquired if the ASQ [Ages and Stages Questionnaire, measuring child development milestones] has been validated in India or not. As evaluator 1 pointed out, a cut-off for below expected milestones would be very useful for helping your interpretation. Is this transfer "accelerating" child development or bringing it in line with where it "should" be according to pre-existing standards. The comments on the usage of the ASQ scores as an outcome are very valuable. If you have not yet age-standardized scores, may I suggest installing (via ssc) using the user-written (by me!) Stata program `stndzxage`. The included PDF tutorial illustrates why standardizing by age is important. Additionally, you may wish to divide your standardization procedure into two age groups, with the cut-off where the number of questions change. And definitely consider how the correlation of the subcategories of the ASQ impacts your findings in that table. You may consider decreasing p-value cut-offs to take into account multiple hypothesis testing.

Both evaluators mentioned including flow charts: a consort diagram (evaluator 1) and a DAG (evaluator 2). While you may not use these in your final paper, as you move your findings from academic publications to those directly engaging with policy makers, these sorts of diagrams can be useful to help the audience grasp your processes.

I agree with evaluator 2 that much more needs to be explored with respect to the empowerment outcomes. You claim that this is a very large amount of money – do these empowerment findings align with what other literature has explored? Maybe they "should" be larger. See Peterman et. al.'s review on "Social Safety Nets, Women's Economic Achievements and Agency: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis" <https://ideas.repec.org/p/cgd/wpaper/684.html>. They likely have a new version; you may wish to email the authors. If you are seeking an additional author from India, this would be a great area of the paper to develop.

The point about the impacts being clinically meaningful is important (Evaluator 1). Another option besides extrapolating to other outcomes such as IQ, kindergarten readiness, or future earnings is to compare the gains from this transfer to the gains from preschool or other child development programs – which is more cost effective with respect to child development? On the other hand, which is better for women’s empowerment?

Note: Further “miscellaneous” comments and suggestions were shared directly with the authors.

Footnotes

1. This abstract was written by David Reinstein [↵](#)
2. We asked them to rank this paper “heuristically” as a percentile “relative to all serious research in the same area that you have encountered in the last three years.” We requested they “consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice. [↵](#)
3. See ranking tiers discussed [here](#). [↵](#)
4. Note: if you are reading this before, or soon after this has been publicly released, the ratings from this paper may not yet have been incorporated into that data presentation. [↵](#)
5.
Judge the quality of the research heuristically. Consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice.

[↵](#)

6. “Do the authors do a good job of (i) stating their main questions and claims, (ii) providing strong evidence and powerful approaches to inform these, and (iii) correctly characterizing the nature of their evidence?”

This was on the newer form only [↵](#)

7.

To what extent does the project contribute to the field or to practice, particularly in ways that are directly or indirectly relevant to global priorities and impactful interventions?

[↵](#)

8. Are methods clearly justified and explained? Are methods and their underlying assumptions reasonable? Are the results likely to be robust to changes in the assumptions? Have the authors avoided bias and questionable research practices? [↵](#)

9. Are concepts clearly defined? Is the reasoning transparent? Are conclusions consistent with the evidence (or formal proofs) presented? Are the data and/or analysis, including tables and figures, relevant to the argument? [↔](#)

10.

Would another researcher be able to replicate the analysis? Are the method and its details explained sufficiently? Is the source of the data clear? Is the data made as widely available as possible, with clear labeling and explanation? Do the authors provide resources that are likely to enable future research and meta-analysis?

[↔](#)

11. There is critical information about the intervention that would make it impossible to replicate the study. My score here reflects this opinion. As for replicating the analysis, I do think it would be possible. [↔](#)

12.

Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic and relevant to practitioners?

[↔](#)

13.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

"Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?"

"Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" [↔](#)

14. Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions? [↔](#)

15.

The latter ratings were merged in the newer form

"Are the paper's chosen topic and approach likely to be useful to global priorities, cause prioritization, and high-impact interventions?"

"Does the paper consider real-world relevance and deal with policy and implementation questions? Are the setup, assumptions, and focus realistic? Do the authors report results that are relevant to practitioners? Do they provide useful quantified estimates (costs, benefits, etc.)?" [↵](#)

16.

The evaluator was given the following instructions:

Identify the most important and impactful factual claim this research makes – e.g., a binary claim or a point estimate or prediction.

Please state the authors' claim precisely and quantitatively. Identify the source of the claim (i.e., cite the paper), and briefly mention the evidence underlying this. We encourage you to explain why you believe this claim is important, either here, or in the text of your report. [↵](#)

17. Evaluators were asked: To what extent do you **believe** the claim you stated above? Feel free to express this either a. in terms of the probability of the claim being true, b. as a credible interval for the parameter being estimated, or c. however you feel comfortable. [↵](#)

18.

We asked:

[Optional] What additional information, evidence, replication, or robustness check would make you substantially more (or less) confident in this claim?

Feel free to refer to the main body of your evaluation here; you don't need to repeat yourself. Please specify how you would perform this robustness check (etc.) as precisely as you are willing. E.g., if you suggest a particular estimation command in a statistical package, this could be very helpful for future robustness replication work. [↵](#)

19.

We asked:

[Optional] Identify the important **implication** of the above claim for funding and policy choices? To what extent do you **believe** this implication? How should it inform policy choices?

Note: this 'implication' could be suggested by the evaluation manager in some cases. As an example of an 'implication' ... in a global health context, the 'main claim' might suggest that a vitamin supplement intervention, if scaled up, would save lives at a \$XXXXX per life saved.

We did not ask this in the 'applied stream' as it is most likely redundant.

⇐

References

1. Weaver, J., Sukhtankar, S., Niehaus, P., & Muralidharan, K. (2024). *Maternal Cash Transfers for Gender Equity and Child Development: Experimental Evidence from India* (Working Paper No. 32093). National Bureau of Economic Research. <https://doi.org/10.3386/w32093> ⇐